

Synthesis and crystal structure of a Cd^{II}-based 2D coordination polymer and determination of band gap[†]

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A new coordination polymer, [Cd(2-ab)₂]_n, (**1**; 2-ab = 2-amino benzoate) has been synthesized by the reaction of 2-aminobenzoic acid (2-aba) with Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O. Single crystal X-ray crystallographic structure determination reveals that **1** has two-dimensional (2D) sheet structure with (4,4) square grid net. Besides, there have been an extensive H-bonding and C-H···π interactions present in the supramolecular network of **1**. Band gap calculation by density functional theory (DFT) computation reveals that the compound **1** possesses semiconducting property. The experimental band gap has also been determined by optical study and the value has a good agreement with the theoretical calculation.

Keywords: Cadmium, coordination polymer, crystal structure, hydrogen bonding, (4,4) net topology.

Introduction

The major part of name of inorganic chemistry belongs to coordination chemistry. The application and academic interest of coordination chemistry have been enriched day-by-day for the structural diversity of coordination compounds¹⁻³. In recent time, researchers are interested to design polymeric coordination compounds composed of metal ions (or metal clusters) and organic ligands (mono or polydentate). In these compounds, metal ions act as nodes and organic ligands act as connectors generating the possibility of formation of one-dimensional (1D) to three-dimensional (3D) coordination polymers (CPs)⁴⁻⁶. The structural diversity of these compounds demands themselves as the active participant in the function of application. Interestingly, these types of materials have the broad area of potential applications: drug delivery, gas storage and separation, magnetism, catalysis, sensing, conductivity and biological applications⁷⁻¹⁵. By using the property of low solubility and inertness towards the acid or base, these polymeric materials have been devoted for the application in semiconducting materials and electronic devices¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Varieties of structures can be obtained by judicious choice of metal ions and organic ligands.

In this regard, various supramolecular interactions including hydrogen bonding, C-H···π, π···π, halogen··halogen and halogen··π play important role during the formation of higher dimensional CPs¹⁹⁻²¹. Coordinating approach of organic ligand is one of the important aspects during the formation of these hybrid materials. However, researchers are interested in mixed organic ligands or mixed functionalities in a single ligand for the fabrication of desired structures^{22,23}. Recently, we have reported a series of CPs which undergo non-covalent interactions to furnish higher dimensional supramolecular architectures²⁴⁻²⁷.

In the present work, we have introduced 2-aminobenzoic acid (2-aba) which is a biologically active molecule containing two active functional groups (-NH₂ and -COOH). Due to presence of two functional groups, 2-aba molecule has enormous contribution towards synthetic organic chemistry, especially for the synthesis of azo dye or Schiff base compounds. Haendler *et al.*, reported the Cu^{II}- and Zn^{II}-based complexes of 2-aba ligand^{28,29}. Herein, we report the synthesis of a Cd^{II}-based two-dimensional (2D) CP[Cd(2-ab)₂]_n, (**1**; 2-ab = 2-amino benzoate) using bi-functional 2-aba ligand. The connectivity of -NH₂ and -COOH groups of 2-aba ligand

[†]Invited Lecture.

with Cd^{II} metal ions fabricate 2D sheet structure with (4,4) square grid net topology. The band gap measurement calculated by density functional theory (DFT) computations confirms the semiconducting properties of the material.

Experimental

General:

All chemicals purchased were reagent grade and were used without further purification. Elemental analysis (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) was performed on a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. Infrared spectrum in KBr (4500–500 cm⁻¹) was recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrometer RX1 spectrometer.

Synthesis of compound:

Compound 1: A solution of 2-aba (0.028 g, 0.2 mmol) neutralized with Et₃N (0.021 g, 0.2 mmol) in EtOH (2 mL) was slowly and carefully layered over a solution of Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (0.062 g, 0.2 mmol), in H₂O (2 mL) using 2 mL 1:1 (v/v) buffer solution of MeOH and H₂O. The dark coloured needle shaped crystals of [Cd(2-aba)₂]_n, (**1**) were obtained after three days (0.050 g, Yield 65%).

Elemental analysis (%) Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂CdN₂O₄: C, 43.67; H, 3.11; N, 7.27. Found: C, 43.57; H, 3.85; N, 7.52; IR (KBr pellet, cm⁻¹): 1590 ν_{as}(COO⁻), 1322 ν_{sym}(COO⁻).

Crystal structure determination:

Single crystal of the compound **1** having suitable dimensions was used for data collection using a Bruker SMART APEX II diffractometer equipped with graphite-monochromated MoKα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). The molecular structure was solved using the SHELX-97 package³⁰. Non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. Hydrogen atoms were placed in their geometrically idealized positions and constrained to ride on their parent atoms. The crystallographic data for **1** are summarized in Table 1 and selected bond lengths and bond angles are given in Table 2.

Theoretical calculation:

During theoretical calculation, GAUSSIAN-09³¹ program package was used to optimize the molecular geometry of the compound **1**. Here, DFT-B3LYP³² functional was used throughout the calculations. LanL2DZ basis set was allotted for all the elements. To commit the electronic transitions, time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT)³³ formalism of

Table 1. Crystal data and refinement parameters for compound **1**

Formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ CdN ₂ O ₄ (1)
fw	384.67
Cryst syst	monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /c
a (Å)	12.998(19)
b (Å)	5.153(7)
c (Å)	9.498(13)
β (deg)	91.06(2)
V (Å ³)	636.0(15)
Z	2
D _{calcd} (g/cm ³)	2.008
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.735
λ (Å)	0.71073
Data [I > 2σ(I)]/params	1116/98
GOF on F ²	1.274
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)] ^{a,b}	R ₁ = 0.0367 wR ₂ = 0.0935
^a R ₁ = Σ F _o - F _c / Σ F _o , ^b wR ₂ = [Σw(F _o ² - F _c ²) ² / Σw(F _o ²) ²] ^{1/2}	

Table 2. Selected bond lengths and bond angles in **1** and **2**

Compound 1			
Cd(1)-O(1)	2.233(4)	O(1)-Cd(1)-O(2)d	87.32(10)
Cd(1)-N(1)c	2.284(5)	N(1)-Cd(1)-N(1)c	180.00
Cd(1)-N(1)	2.284(5)	O(2)a-Cd(1)-N(1)c	91.32(13)
Cd(1)-O(2)d	2.279(5)	O(1)c-Cd(1)-O(2)d	92.68(11)
Cd(1)-O(2)a	2.279(5)	O(1)-Cd(1)-O(1)c	180.00
Cd(1)-O(1)c	2.233(4)	N(1)-Cd(1)-O(2)a	88.68(13)
O(1)-Cd(1)-N(1)	77.67(12)	N(1)-Cd(1)-O(2)d	91.32(13)
O(1)-Cd(1)-N(1)c	102.33(12)	O(2)a-Cd(1)-O(2)d	180.00(16)
N(1)-Cd(1)-O(1)c	102.33(12)	N(1)c-Cd(1)-O(2)d	88.68(13)
O(2)a-Cd(1)-O(1)c	87.32(10)	N(1)-C(1)-C(2)	118.5(4)
O(1)c-Cd(1)-N(1)c	77.67(12)	N(1)-C(1)-C(6)	121.9(4)
O(1)-Cd(1)-O(2)a	92.68(10)	C(2)-C(1)-C(6)	119.5(4)
Symmetry code: a = 1-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z; b = 1-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z; c = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z; d = x, 3/2-y, -1/2+z			

the compound were performed. Gauss sum³⁴ was done to calculate theoretical electronic spectra and molecular orbital contribution from composition.

Results and discussion

Description of structure:

Structural description of [Cd(2-aba)₂] (**1**):

X-Ray crystallography revealed that the compound **1** crys-

tallizes in the monoclinic space group $P2_1/c$ with $Z = 2$. The asymmetric unit in **1** contains of distorted octahedral Cd^{II} centre ligated by two O atoms and two N atoms from two 2-aba ligands in η^2 fashion in the equatorial plane and by two O atoms from two different 2-aba ligands at the axial sites in η^1 manner (Fig. 1a). It is observed that bond length Cd-O is distance varying from 2.233(4) to 2.279(5) Å and Cd-N bond length is found to be 2.284(5) Å. The connectivity of 2-aba ligands with Cd^{II} centers results in 2D sheet structure with (4,4) square grid net (Figs. 1b and 1c), using TOPOS pro-

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 1. (a) A view showing coordination environment of Cd^{II} centre in compound **1**. (b) 2D Polymeric structure of compound **1** viewed along *a*-axis. (c) Square grid (4,4) net structure of **1**.

gram³⁵. In the solid-state structure, the 2D sheet undergoes gigantic supramolecular contacts via hydrogen bonding and C-H \cdots π interactions (Fig. 2). -NH₂ group undergoes intra and intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions with O atoms of -COOH groups of 2-aba ligands with N \cdots O separations of 2.876(6)–3.046(7) Å.

Fig. 2. (a) Intramolecular hydrogen bonding and C-H \cdots π interactions in 2D polymeric structure of compound **1**.

Optical study:

The optical spectrum of **1** has been recorded using film of dispersed material (in DMF) in the range 200–550 nm. The absorption spectrum of **1** exhibits strong energy absorption in the visible region at ~3370 nm. The optical band gap of the compound was assessed using Tauc's equation³⁶.

$$\alpha \cdot hv = A(hv - E_g)^n \quad (1)$$

All the parameters in this equation have their usual significances. A is a constant which is considered as **1** for the ideal case. Here, the value of the exponent n in the above equation was considered as $n = 1/2$. By extrapolating the linear region of the plot $(\alpha \cdot hv)^2$ vs hv (Fig. 3) to $\alpha = 0$ absorption, the values of direct optical band gap (E_g) of **1** was evaluated as 3.34 eV.

DFT Computation and band gap:

In this experiment, lattice matching and deformation potentials have been used to obtain the Schottky electrical contact. The deformation commonly states the energy gap between valence and conduction band which is normally the difference between highest occupied and lowest unoccupied

Fig. 3. Tauc's plots and UV-Vis absorption spectra (inset) for 1.

molecular orbital energy values ($\Delta E = E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$, eV). Here, the ΔE value has been calculated as 3.97 eV (Fig. 4) which is in good consistency with the value obtained from Tauc's plot. In case of CPs, the absolute deformation potentials (ADPs) are used during the obtaining of band gap³⁷. As the CP has hybrid nature; therefore, the band gap has been affected by the electronic nature of both the materials. In CPs of d^{10} metal system, the band edges are often determined by electronic states of organic ligand along with the geometry strain of the framework^{38,39}.

Table 3. DFT table of compound 1

MO	Energy (eV)	Cd	Ligand
LUMO+5	-0.52	42	58
LUMO+4	-0.9	01	99
LUMO+3	-1.12	05	95
LUMO+2	-1.53	01	99
LUMO+1	-1.92	01	99
LUMO	-2.03	00	100
HOMO	-6.00	00	100
HOMO-1	-6.03	00	100
HOMO-2	-6.37	00	100
HOMO-3	-6.52	02	98
HOMO-4	-6.65	01	99
HOMO-5	-7.15	00	100

Nature of key transitions: ILCT; ILCT: Intra ligand charge transfer transition.

Fig. 4. DFT computed energy of molecular orbitals (MOs) and the energy difference between HOMO and LUMO of the compound 1.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a Cd^{II} -based 2D CP has been synthesized using bi-functional 2-aba ligand and characterized by X-ray crystallography. The compound adopts a 2D sheet structure with (4,4) net topology. There have been intramolecular hydrogen bonding and $\text{C-H}\cdots\pi$ interactions present in the 2D layer structure. The semiconducting behaviour of the compound has been realised by the band gap calculation using DFT computations. Here, short metal to metal contact may be responsible for the semiconducting nature of the compound.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC Nos. 1820722.

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J. Indian Chem. Soc., Vol. 95, December 2018

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